

COMPARING “MY HEART IN THE HIGHLANDS” BY ROBERT BURNS AND “IQROR” BY MUHAMMAD YUSUF

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Abstract

In this article, main differences and similarities has been studied in the examples of poetry of Robert Burns and Muhammad Yusuf. The peculiarities of the poems of both authors have been revealed according to the structure, stylistic devices and rhyming scheme.

Keywords: poetry, works of Robert Burns, “Iqror” by Muhammad Yusuf, comparison of Uzbek and English poetry, poem.

Introduction

Every nation has seen its own masters of pen and line. While comparing the poetry of an English-speaking country and Uzbekistan, undoubtedly illustrates silhouettes of Scottish poet Robert Burns and Uzbek poet Muhammad Yusuf. These poets not only lived, albeit a short, yet dignified life, but left behind a diverse creative heritage. Each of them, in his own way, understood and raised the theme of the love for their homeland in their works. The article discusses differences and similarities between two works: “My Heart in the Highlands” by Robert Burns and “Iqror” by Muhammad Yusuf.

Main part

Robert Burns is a poet of Scotland, perhaps there is no other poet who would be known and sung for two centuries. He wrote most of his poems in Scottish dialect, and main characters of his works were ordinary Scots: hard working, poor but with kind hearts that know no greed and love their motherland, their freedom. The poem “My Heart in the Highlands” discusses love for the homeland, pride being one of the sons of this land:

“The birth-place of valour, the country of worth;”

Uzbek poet Muhammad Yusuf in his works describes countrymen’s life, naïve first love, love for the mother, philosophical notions in “Yangi Yil Kechasi”, in “Do’ppi” and “Belbog” fear for nation to lose its origins, traditions and culture. In “Iqror” Muhammad Yusuf similar to Burns proclaims his love for Uzbekistan, homesickness, his longing to return home after a long journey:

“Na gapga ko’nayin, Na til bilayin,
Ko’zdan uyqu qochdi, dildan halovat -
Uch kunda sog’insam nima qilayin,
Chala qolar bo’ldi hamma sayohat.”

In “My Heart in the Highlands” Robert Burns was sorry to part with his favorite places, with the northern nature, and his deep feelings for the land, nostalgia pushed him to write this poem. Burn’s homeland and nature are bundled together in an enlightening manner, since this is not about specific historical and political matters, but about the eternal, “natural” way of life of a mountain Scotsman, not affected by modern trends:

“My heart’s in the Highlands, a-chasing the deer;
A-chasing the wild deer, and following the roe,”

The poem is not just about the “mountains”, but about the Highlands- the northern, mountainous, “prehistoric” part of Scotland. In the minds of Scotsman, Highlands is opposed to Lowlands- the southern, flat, more developed part of Scotland, both in agriculture and industrial relations. Although the south offers great opportunities, but the north is the birthplace of the lyrical character, his heart has remained forever there:

“Wherever I wander, wherever I rove,
The hills of the Highlands forever I love.”

Muhammad Yusuf declares the same faithfulness for his homeland, viewing the land as a person, as his guide, teacher and mentor without whom (the land) he would be miserable:

“Qayga borsam suyab, boshni tik tut deb,
Tog'laring ortimdan ergashib yurar.”

Both poems are great sample of civic lyrics that combines pathetics and tenderness. Whereas “Iqror” is more like an ode, “My Heart in the Highlands” is both like a hymn and a simple song of a shepherd. In both authors themselves are narrators as they use “I”. Robert Burns speaks about his birth land, and Muhammad Yusuf describes places and countries he visited in real life.

Burns is, as a narrator of the poem, such a combination of striking traits, like a character drawn from an eighteenth-century sentimental novel, attractive yet forbidding, peculiar yet strangely appealing. Muhammad Yusuf gives us vivid images that we easily can relate to. Burns wrote the poem as ideal lyrics for the Scotland’s folklore songs, while Muhammad Yusuf commune with his fellow countrymen through the poem as it is simple and moving, although not as unique. Maybe, that trivial things are the reason why every and any one can relate to them:

“Parijning eng go‘zal restoranlarin,
Bitta tandiringga alishmasmanmen.”

Where Burns poem falls under pastoral poetry’s category, whereas Muhammad Yusuf’s “Iqror” is free verse:

“Farewell to the mountains high cover’d with snow; a
Farewell to the straths and green valleys below; a
Farewell to the forests and wild-hanging woods; b
Farewell to the torrents and loud-pouring floods:” b

In the second stanza Burns uses anaphora, repeating the word “farewell” to emphasis his mourning, his longing, but rather impossibility at the moment, to be back in the Highlands. On the other hand, Muhammad Yusuf uses diacope, which lays emphasis on his homeland being “the one” and others being for him foreign in every sense.

“Bir go‘sha suv bo‘lsa, bir go‘sha qirlar, a
Qancha yurtni ko‘rdim, qancha taqdirlar a
Qayga borsam suyab, boshni tik tut deb, b
Tog'laring ortimdan ergashib yurar.” a

The rhyming scheme in the second stanzas below show us that while Burns uses **aabb** , Muhammad Yusuf uses **aaba** rhyming scheme as in rubaiyat.

Conclusion

Thus, the poems of Robert Burns and Muhammad Yusuf are not so different in mood and both have feeling of nostalgia and homesickness. Also, both works, ideological in content, use the

description of their homeland is an opportunity to talk about person's world, his soul and relationship with the land itself. Authors have similar worldview as they praise national features, traditions and language. The poem "Iqror" leaves readers optimistic with the idea that in the future author somehow would be back in his homeland. In the poem "My Heart in the Highlands" readers left saddened with the understanding of author's farewell. Similarities between two novel's strike the reader instantly, but in closer consideration there are some significant differences between them.

References:

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